

EU MAP webinar: Mountain value chains – heterogeneity and innovation

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

16 December 2021

The first **MOVING** (MOuntain Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth) **EU Multi-Actor Platform webinar** on Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation took place on 16 December 2021. The event gathered around 60 attendees from different backgrounds.

The main objectives of this webinar were:

- Present the MOVING project and publicise the **EU-MAP**;
- showcase specific traditional or emerging value chains (VCs) working on innovation and resilience to climate change and social changes;
- enhance the exchange, learn and interact at the EU level on heterogeneity and innovation in mountain value chains.

During the webinar, two presentations focused on the first year of progress and results of the project and its Community of Practice (CoP).

The event featured other presentations on mountain value chains (VCs) of three **reference regions** of the project, which showed the heterogeneity and different levels of innovation: (i) Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham value chain; (ii) Speyside Malt Whisky value chain and (iii) Certified Ecotourism Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains value chain.

The webinar concluded with a round table discussion with representatives from University of Cordoba (Spain), University of Pisa (Italy), Highclere Consulting (Romania), The James Hutton Institute (United Kingdom) and AEIDL (Belgium) where they talked about heterogeneity and innovation in mountain value chains, as well as their current needs, challenges and opportunities.

ORGANISER:

16 DECEMBER 2021

ONLINE

64 PARTICIPANTS
(research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

18 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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If you see this icon, click to see the video

GETTING TO KNOW MOVING

MOVING: first year of progress and results

María del Mar DELGADO

MOVING Coordinator, University of Cordoba

Mar Delgado from the University of Cordoba presented the project and its first year of progress and results.

MOVING is a Horizon 2020 project that started in September 2020 and will last until the end of August 2024. It is a research and innovation action coordinated by the University of Cordoba (Spain), and it gathers 23 partner organisations.

The project selected 23 mountain Reference Regions in 16 countries, which represent the wide diversity of mountain areas in Europe. In these regions, the project is rolling-out its research activities and actions engaging relevant stakeholders through 24 Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs).

The project aims to build capacities and co-develop a sound evidence-base to support the policy frameworks that address mountain areas' needs across Europe. It is analysing existing value chains and identifying new or upgraded ones that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas, valorising local assets, and delivering private and public goods.

In relation to the key research activities that MOVING project has carried out so far, Ms Delgado highlighted the MOVING Conceptual and Analytical Framework (CAF) and the work behind the Inventory of mountain value chains, where MOVING has screened more than 450 traditional, emerging and innovative value chains in European mountain areas.

Other deliverables have been finalised, such as the initial set of Policy Briefs; the land use systems and land cover maps in 23 Reference Regions, and the list of selected value chains and relationship building.

The project co-creates the required knowledge and data with local actors through MAPs. The project has started a spatial and participatory analysis of vulnerabilities and resilience, to climate change and other relevant threats, of land use, production systems, and value chains in each of the 23 selected Reference Regions.

In addition, MOVING is going to start to produce and provide interactive visual tools such as MOVING Mountains App and an open tool for visualisation of georeferenced data.

MOVING: Community of Practice and the EU Multi-Actor Platform

Blanca CASARES

EU MAP Coordinator, AEIDL

Blanca Casares from AEIDL presented the MOVING Community of Practice (CoP), which is a core feature of the project. It is understood as a European-wide Science-Society-Policy interface to engage different stakeholders around resilience to climate change and social change of mountain value chains.

In practice, the CoP includes 23 regional Multi-Actor Platform (MAPs), established in the 23 Reference Regions, and one European-level Multi-Actor Platform (EU MAP). In this first year of the project, progress has been made in setting up all of them. MOVING will connect research, policy and society through its 24 Multi-Actor Platforms.

The EU MAP offers an open space to stakeholders that are interested to exchange, learn and interact at the EU level to: (a) contribute to key MOVING deliverables; (b) support peer-to-peer exchanges on additional topics relevant for the members and for the regional MAPs; and (c) create a long-lasting community.

Among the different activities and contacts that have taken place this year, she mentioned the MOVING contribution to the EU Roadmap for sustainable carbon cycles. MOVING's feedback focuses on recommendations to improve mountain management and reduce the risks that mountains face due to climate change.

In addition, she referred to the article and infographic produced in collaboration with Mountain Partnership (FAO) for the International Mountain Day.

Meet, share, exchange and learn from relevant European players. Join the EU MAP by expressing your interest [here](#).

GETTING TO KNOW MOVING's VALUE CHAINS

Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham value chain

Sherman FARHAD

Member of the coordinating team of Sierra Morena reference region, University of Cordoba

Sherman Farhad from the University of Cordoba presented the work being carried out in [Sierra Morena Reference Region](#) on the Los Pedroches protected designation of origin (PDO) Iberian Ham value chain. The project has started a deep participatory and extended value chain analysis.

The region, located in the south-west of the Iberian Peninsula, is part of a unique landscape in Spain called Dehesa. Dehesas are a multi-functional agro-silvo-pastoral system where agriculture, forestry and grazing are combined.

She explained the territorial importance of Iberian ham and the relevance of the PDO certification in this value chain. She also highlighted that the final product of this VC (Iberian Ham) is considered a healthy and top quality product due to its unsaturated fat marbling, which is the result of: 1) unique traditional Iberian pigs breed, 2) raised under extensive systems, and 3) fed with specific diet based on acorns from holm oak trees.

In relation to stakeholder participation, the Multi-Actor Platform is composed of a diverse group of actors from different stages of the Iberian ham VC.

Regarding the first results of the participatory vulnerability analysis, acorn production has been identified as the key reference variable. The main concern in the region is the loss of the holm oak trees

(from which acorns are obtained) due to a root pathogen called Phytophthora cinnamomic. She presented as main causes for tree loss: droughts and higher temperatures (due to climate change), poor soil management and pruning, and stocking density. Additionally, lack of generational replacement and the consequent loss of dehesa management knowledge are also threatening the future of the region.

Among the main elements of innovation, Sherman pointed out: (a) digitalisation, (b) PDO certification (Los Pedroches), (c) processing infrastructure and export, (d) e-commerce.

Finally, she concluded by highlighting the key opportunity that MOVING provides to deeply analyse the Iberian ham VC (practices, actors, values, opportunities and challenges, etc.), hand-in-hand with the regional MAP members, to hopefully co-create conducive policy environments, capable to support local actors in their practices, innovations, and adaptation capacities; and finally to contribute to the resilient and sustainable future of the Sierra Morena mountain region.

Find out more about the Sierra Morena Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional Multi-Actor Platform (MAP), [here](#).

Speyside Malt Whisky value chain

Kirsty BLACKSTOCK

Coordinator of Highland and Islands reference region, The James Hutton Institute

Kirsty Blackstock from The James Hutton Institute provided a presentation about the work being carried out in a specific part of the [Highlands and Islands Reference Region](#), the Speyside Malt Whisky value chain. She explained all the practices involved in Speyside Whisky in the different stages of the chain: production, processing, distribution and marketing, and consumption.

She described the extended value chain, emphasising the importance of territorial capital (water quality and quantity, as well as mountain imaginaries at resource and landscape level), and the connections up and down the catchment area (primary, manufacturing and service) and between local SMEs and multinationals.

In addition, she provided an overview of the distribution of distilleries in the Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) and the connection between distilleries, land cover and land use, which influence the quality and quantify of water on which the VC depends. Regarding vulnerability to environmental change, she explained that it is necessary to consider spring and surface water, to understand how different factors influence water in order to identify the perception of exposure, to discuss the VC's sensitivity to exposure and adaptive capacity of the Whisky Industry. The factors considered include: muirburn, snowmelt, peat soil condition, rainfall, land use

change, water temperature, air temperature, extreme events and overexploitation.

In relation to stakeholder participation, the Multi-Actor Platform is composed by a diverse group of actors mainly related to endogenous resources and enabling environment.

In terms of areas to explore, she pointed out: re-localising the benefits of the VC for the local population, different approaches to innovation for net zero emissions (such as distillery innovations or wider catchment restoration) and the identification and support of new alliances. She also talked about areas to explore related to innovation for net zero emissions such as distillery innovations and investment in catchment restoration.

Finally, she concluded that: (a) value chains are a complementary perspective on uplands in Scotland; (b) communities of practice can translate research into action across separate policy and business silos; and (c) localised benefits of global value chain are of value for the people of Spey.

Find out more about the Highland and Islands Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional Multi-Actor Platform (MAP), [here](#).

GETTING TO KNOW MOVING's VALUE CHAINS

Certified ecotourism Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains value chain

Cătălina ROGOZAN

Member of the coordinating team of Southern Romanian Carpathian mountains reference region, Highclere Consulting

Cătălina Rogozan from Highclere Consulting presented the work being carried out in the [Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains Reference Region](#) on the Certified ecotourism value chain.

She provided information on the location of the region and more specifically on the Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) as well as its area, population and average income. The land use system is a mosaic landscape with forest and extensive semi-natural grassland. The reference variable in the ongoing analysis is landscape composition.

Following this, she delved into the question of why certified ecotourism is important. The Piatra Craiului National Park represents a high quality tourist destination, but also a fragile landscape and a vulnerable ecosystem that is under great pressure from inappropriate development.

The Piatra Craiului region is one of ten 'ecodestinations' promoted by the Association of Ecotourism in Romania (AER). Certified ecotourism has great potential to contribute to the sustainability and resilience of the region.

Stakeholders to be engaged include producers (farmers and foresters), public authorities/policy makers, researchers, innovation brokers/advisors, business, NGOs, etc.

The current and emerging vulnerabilities are changing land use and the landscape due to: (i) over-exploitation of forest and other local resources, (ii) abandonment of less accessible grasslands in the mountains and decline in traditional farming, (iii) chaotic development of leisure, recreation and tourism activities, and (iv) poor construction of tourist accommodation and holiday homes. Another risk identified is the impact of climate change (extreme rainfall and flooding, raising temperatures and risk of wildfires).

Finally, regarding future perspectives, she concluded that a more strategic and integrated approach to local sustainable development is needed, including social, economic, environmental and governance aspects.

Traditions are deeply rooted, and local people are very resistant to change - this is both a strength and a weakness. But how do we engage local people in building sustainability and resilience?

Find out more about the Highland and Islands Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional Multi-Actor Platform (MAP), [here](#).

ROUND TABLE

Mountain value chains - heterogeneity and innovation

Mar Delgado and Sherman Farhad from University of Cordoba
 Gianluca Brunori from University of Pisa, Cătălina Rogozan and Mark Redman from Highclere Consulting, Kirsty Blackstock from The James Hutton Institute, and Blanca Casares and Robin Salter from AEIDL

Mountain areas face different social, economic and environmental challenges to innovation and improving their resilience and sustainability. During the round table, various topics were discussed and seminar participants were given space to intervene.

Key take-home messages include:

There are grounds to **explore and question the processes of different quality schemes**, such as the regulation of Protected Designations of Origin (PDO). Consideration of the code of practice and the certification process is needed. A strong link is required between the governance of VCs and the governance of the place, and the between rural areas and other areas. It is important to investigate the potential of this code of practice in relation to broader societal challenges.

There is also room to **analyse the degree of adaptation and flexibility** in these processes and regulations.

Working at different levels allows improvement of the governance mechanism of the value chain at different levels, from production to consumption, which is linked to transferring the value to the end consumer. This is what MOVING will work on through its multi-actor platforms (MAPs).

New generations of policies and initiatives are needed in an inclusive way for mountain areas. Mainly that mountains require a joined up approach across different policies and strategies. The project will build on the momentum of policies and initiatives being developed at European level. For example,

the new **Common Agricultural Policy**, the **Green Deal** (especially the **Farm to Fork** and **Biodiversity 2030** strategies) and **the long-term vision for rural areas** (LTVRA) do not directly address mountains, so there is a need for MOVING to make recommendations and use its results to support a specific policy roadmap for mountain areas.

It is important to **make clear in the policy framework, even at European level, the need to consider the VCs as broader than supply chain management**. This framework should be implemented in local strategies, to improve the strategic capacity of locals in mountains areas.

A collective effort is needed to **make mountain areas attractive** to both the traditional population and the new generations. In addition, it is necessary to **maintain traditional knowledge and strengthen the capacity of the communities** that inhabit these areas.

Main impact and contribution of MOVING:

In addition to all the results of the different research activities, the main contribution is the co-development of knowledge regarding the interaction of value chains in the socio-ecological system (SES) that makes up a mountain area, and how they can contribute to the sustainable future of these territories.

The project will also contribute to future perspectives of these areas through the design of scenarios to 2050, and the identification of policy gaps and building blocks for the new generation of policies that enhance the resilience and sustainability of mountain regions.

Do you want to know more about the project and the community? Find more information, [here](#).
 Join the EU MAP by expressing your interest, [here](#).
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